

Development of EGFR Targeting Peptide/Chlorin e6 Conjugates for Targeted Antitumor Activity on Breast Cancer

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Abstract

Breast cancer is considered the primary cause of cancer-related deaths in women. Conventionally, different treatment strategies such as hormone therapy, radiation therapy, surgical operations and chemotherapy are utilized in the treatment of breast cancer. Although, chemotherapy aims to kill cancerous cells by interfering with DNA synthesis and cell divisions leads to damage to healthy tissues as well as tumor tissues. Considering the side effects of the conventional treatments, developing novel alternative methods is crucial for breast cancer treatment. Photodynamic therapy (PDT) has emerged as a promising new approach due to its suitability for localized treatments. Chlorin e6 (Ce6), a porphyrin-derived photosensitizer that is frequently preferred in PDT applications, accumulates effectively on tumors. However, the anti-tumor effect of Ce6 is frequently restricted due to its poor targeting of cancer cells and toxicity to the healthy cells. Therefore, the combination of Ce6 with a tumor cell-specific agent may prevent the damage to healthy tissues by ensuring targeted application. GE11 peptide, a breast cancer targeting peptide, binds to epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) that is overexpressed in epithelial originated tumors including breast cancer. In this study, novel GE11-Ce6 conjugates that are able to specifically target breast cancer were synthesized and characterization of GE11-Ce6 conjugates was carried out by examining the FT-IR spectrum. Confocal fluorescence microscopy images demonstrated the cellular uptake of GE11-Ce6 conjugates into MDA-MB-231 tumor cells. Confocal images confirmed the enhanced accumulation of Ce6 into breast cancer cells with Ge11-Ce6 conjugates compared to Ce6 alone. Developed novel GE11-Ce6 conjugates have the potential to be an ideal breast cancer targeting antitumor agent.

Keywords: EGFR targeting peptide, photosensitizer, chlorin e6, breast cancer

Introduction

Currently, breast cancer is considered the leading cause of cancer-related deaths in women [1] and each year, 2 to 2.5 million women are diagnosed with breast cancer worldwide [2]. Conventional treatment methods of breast cancer typically involve various strategies such as hormone therapy, radiation therapy, surgical operations, and chemotherapy [3]. However, these conventional treatments lead to several serious side effects. For instance, hormone drugs can cause hot flashes, night sweats, menstrual cycle disruptions, and vaginal dryness, due to the need for long-term use. Besides, although chemotherapy aims to kill cancer cells by interfering with DNA synthesis and cell division, the lack of selectivity towards the cancerous tissues also leads to significant damage to healthy tissues [4]. Moreover, synthetic chemotherapeutic drugs, which are currently utilized in clinical applications, often cause significant challenges such as poor water solubility, drug resistance, short blood circulation time, limited effectiveness and nonspecific distribution [5, 6]. Since these side effects greatly hinder their clinical application on the management of breast cancer, there is an increasing need to develop alternative targeted methods for the breast cancer treatment [3].

Photodynamic therapy (PDT) has emerged as a promising new approach due to its suitability for localized treatments. PDT is a clinically approved, minimally invasive alternative for treating various cancers by targeting tumor cells through the combined use of photosensitizers (PS) and light. When the PS is activated by light, it triggers energy transfer cascades that produce cytotoxic reactive oxygen species, leading to cell death [7]. Chlorine e6 (Ce6), a porphyrin-derived hydrophilic photosensitizer that is frequently preferred in PDT applications, accumulates very effectively on tumors and can strongly absorb longer wavelengths (670 nm) [8]. However, Ce6 possess some disadvantages such as low water solubility and accumulation in healthy cells as well as cancerous cells. Consequently, when exposed to light, it may lead to undesired toxic effects to healthy tissue [9]. Thus, the combination of Ce6 with a tumor cell-specific agent may prevent the damage to healthy tissue, improving targeted application [10].

In recent years, peptides that can specifically target cancer cells are frequently preferred for targeted application. Among these peptides, the GE11 peptide stands out for its ability to bind specifically to the epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR or ErbB1), which is overexpressed in many epithelial-origin tumors, including breast cancer. The peptide sequence YHWYGYTPENVI has been developed as the 22nd analogue of the GE11 peptide, showing a 2.6-fold higher uptake by MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells, which is known for their high EGFR expression, compared to the original GE11 peptide. This enhanced targeting capability suggests that using the 22nd analogue of the GE11 peptide in combination with various antitumor agents could be a promising strategy for targeted drug delivery in breast cancer treatment [11].

Herein, we developed novel GE11-Ce6 conjugates that show targeting and effective accumulation on MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell line. GE11-Ce6 conjugates were synthesized by solid phase peptide synthesis and successful conjugation was confirmed via FT-IR spectrum. The effective accumulation of GE11-Ce6 conjugates on the MDA-MB-231 cell line was observed via confocal imaging. GE11-Ce6 conjugates showed more effective accumulation on breast cancer cell lines compared to free form Ce6. The novel GE11-Ce6 conjugates may be promising agents in the management of breast cancer.

Materials and Methods

1. Synthesis of GE11-Ce6 Conjugates Results and Discussion

All the chemicals necessary for peptide synthesis were obtained from AAPPTEC (Louisville, KY, USA). The GE11 peptide with a sequence of YHWYGYTPENVI was synthesized on 4-Methylbenzhydrylamine (MBHA) resin (0.67 mmol g⁻¹ loading capacity) via 9-fluorenylmethoxycarbonyl (Fmoc) chemistry using an automatic peptide synthesizer (AAPPTEC Focus Xi, Louisville, KY, ABD), as previously described [12]. Briefly, 400 mg of resin was swollen in dimethylformamide (DMF) for 30 minutes (min) and washed three times with DMF. Fmoc-protected amino acids (2 equivalents (eq)), 2-(1H-benzotriazole-1-yl)-1,1,3,3-tetramethyluronium hexafluorophosphate (HBTU; 1.95 eq), and N,N-diisopropylethylamine (DIEA; 3 eq) were added to the resin and allowed to react for 1 h. The Kaiser test was performed to check for the presence of unreacted amines. Once the test result was negative, the resin was washed three times with DMF and 20% piperidine diluted in DMF was added to the resin to deprotect the Fmoc groups, allowing it to mix for 30 min. The Kaiser test was repeated to ensure the complete removal of the Fmoc protecting group. Once the coupling of all amino acids was complete, Fmoc was removed for the conjugation of Ce6. To synthesize the GE11-Ce6 conjugates previously described method was utilized [13]. Briefly, EDC/HOBt with a molar ratio of 1:1 were activated in DMF. Thereafter, 5 eq Ce6 and 30 eq of DIEA were added to the solution. The peptide was incubated with the prepared solution overnight for reaction to take place. Afterwards, the GE11-Ce6 conjugate was cleaved from the resin by using a solution containing TFA, TIPS, and H₂O at a ratio of 95:2.5:2.5. The GE11-Ce6 solution was poured into cold ether and the suspension was centrifuged to obtain the GE11-Ce6 as the supernatant. Finally, the peptide solution was frozen at -80°C and lyophilized using a Biobase Biodustry Bk-FD10P lyophilizer (Shandong, China) to obtain the GE11-Ce6 conjugates in powder form.

2. Characterization of GE11-Ce6 Conjugates

Successful conjugation of GE11 peptide and Ce6 was determined by ATR-FTIR spectroscopy. A Nicolet iS5 spectrometer (Thermo Scientific, Madison, WI, USA) was used to obtain FTIR spectra of Ce6 and GE11-Ce6. The spectrometer has a spectral resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and can capture 16 scans in the range 400–4000 cm⁻¹ [14].

To further characterize the successful conjugation the absorption spectra of GE11-Ce6 was obtained by using a Synergy™ HTX Multi-Mode Microplate Reader (BioTek, Winooski, VT, USA). Briefly, GE11-Ce6 conjugates were dissolved in DMSO with a final concentration of 100 µg/ml. UV-VIS spectra were obtained by measuring the absorbance of the obtained solution at 1 nm intervals [15]. The Ce6 amount on GE11-Ce6 conjugates was determined by using the calibration curve of Ce6 at 570 nm. Briefly, Ce6 was dissolved in DMSO with different concentrations between the range of 1-100 µg/ml. The absorbance values of each concentration were obtained at 570 nm by using a multi-mode plate reader. Thereafter, the absorbance value of GE11-Ce6 conjugates with a concentration of 100 µg/ml was obtained at 570 nm and Ce6 amount was calculated by using the calibration curve.

3. Determination of the Cellular Uptake of GE11-Ce6 Conjugates into MDA-MB-321 Cells

MDA-MB-231 cell line was cultured by using Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) (Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, Missouri, USA) as basal medium that is supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany), 1% L-glutamine (Genaxxon BioScience, Ulm, Germany), and 0.1% penicillin/ streptomycin (Genaxxon BioScience, Ulm, Germany) at 37 °C and 5% CO₂.

To determine the cellular uptake of GE11-Ce6 4 main groups was utilized:

1. Ce6/1h: 40 µg/ml Ce6 with 1 hour of incubation with cells
2. Ce6/3h: 40 µg/ml Ce6 with 3 hour of incubation with cells
3. GE11-Ce6/1h: 40 µg/ml Ce6 containing GE11-Ce6 with 1 hour of incubation with cells
4. GE11-Ce6/3h: 40 µg/ml Ce6 containing GE11-Ce6 with 3 hour of incubation with cells

Briefly, cells were seeded on 96 well plates at a density of 5×10^4 and incubated with culture medium for 24 hours at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. Afterwards, cell medium was removed and prepared Ce6 and GE11-Ce6 solutions were added onto cells. The cells were incubated for 1 and 3 hours. Thereafter, MDA-MB-231 cells were washed three times with PBS and then fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde for 15 min. After fixation process, the cell nuclei was stained with DAPI. Finally, the cells were imaged by a confocal microscope. The fluorescence of Ce6 was detected at 546 nm (red) and the fluorescence of DAPI used for nuclear staining was detected at 358 nm (blue) [16].

Results and Discussion

ATR-FTIR spectroscopy was utilized to demonstrate the successful conjugation of Ce6 to GE11 peptide by solid phase peptide synthesis (Figure 1). In the Ce6 FT-IR spectra, functional groups of Ce6 was determined [17]. For instance, the peak at around 1700 cm⁻¹ represents the C=O vibration that is observed due to hydrogen bonds of Ce6. Furthermore, there are several bonds between the 1100-1300 cm⁻¹ region, signifying the presence of CO groups. This region is known as a characteristic region for Ce6 since it signifies the C–O stretching coordinate and COH angles. Moreover, the peaks around 2867 cm⁻¹, 2924 cm⁻¹ and 2966 cm⁻¹ signify the C-H stretching, while the peak near 3300 cm⁻¹ represents the N-H stretch of Ce6. In the FT-IR spectra of GE11-Ce6, the specific peaks representing C–O stretching coordinate and COH angles of Ce6 were observed. Furthermore, the peak near 3300 cm⁻¹ elongated significantly showing the presence of N-H stretch from both Ce6 and GE11 peptide. These results confirmed the successful conjugation.

Figure 1. FTIR spectrum for Ce6 and GE11-Ce6 conjugates

The absorbance spectra of GE11-Ce6 conjugates further confirmed the presence of Ce6 in the GE11-Ce6 conjugates (Figure 2). Ce6 is characterized with a strong Soret band around 400 nm and weaker Q bands around 500 and 670 nm [18]. In the obtained absorbance spectrum both Soret band and Q bands were determined indicating the presence of Ce6 in the conjugates. Furthermore, to calculate the amount of Ce6 in GE11-Ce6 conjugates, a calibration curve of Ce6 was utilized. The amount of Ce6 in 100 µg/ml GE11-Ce6 solution was determined as 32.04 µg/ml and all experiments were carried out according to this calculation.

Figure 2. Absorption spectra of GE11-Ce6 conjugates

The accumulation of free form Ce6 and GE11-Ce6 was visualized by confocal microscopy (Figure 3). The cellular uptake of Ce6 in the developed GE11-Ce6 conjugates was enhanced when compared to the control groups. Confocal microscopy images, taken after 1 and 3 hours of incubation, revealed that the conjugate facilitated a significantly higher accumulation of Ce6 within the MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell line. Specifically, the intensity of red color, which signifies Ce6 fluorescence, was increased in the GE11-Ce6 treated cells, indicating efficient internalization and potential cytoplasmic localization. After 1-hour incubation, a significant difference was observable on GE11-Ce6 compared to Ce6, suggesting rapid uptake kinetics. After 3-hour incubation, the difference was more significant than the first time point, signifying sustained and enhanced uptake over time. Furthermore, Ce6 was not only internalized but also distributed in close proximity to the nuclei in GE11-Ce6 groups, which could imply effective intracellular targeting. These findings showed the enhanced targeting and penetration capacity of Ce6 into the MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell line with the developed GE11-Ce6 conjugates. Therefore, GE11-Ce6 conjugates suggest a promising approach for targeted photodynamic therapy, potentially minimizing side effects and enhancing treatment specificity.

Figure 3. Determination of the accumulation of Ce6 into MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell line by confocal microscopy. Cells were incubated with free Ce6 and GE11-Ce6 conjugates for 1 and 3 hours. The fluorescence of Ce6 was detected at 546 nm (red) and the fluorescence of DAPI used for nuclear staining was detected at 358 nm (blue). Ce6 concentration was adjusted as 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for both groups. Scale bar represents 50 μm .

Conclusion

Efficient and targeted internalization of Ce6 by breast cancer cells is of great importance. Herein, we successfully developed GE11-Ce6 conjugates by solid phase peptide synthesis. The results demonstrated that GE11-Ce6 conjugates significantly enhanced the accumulation of Ce6 molecules in breast cancer cells compared to free Ce6. Consequently, the GE11-Ce6 conjugates significantly improve the delivery and penetration of Ce6 in breast cancer cells, highlighting their potential for targeted photodynamic therapy applications. These findings suggest that GE11-Ce6 conjugates could enhance treatment specificity and efficacy while minimizing off-target effects, offering a promising strategy for cancer therapy.

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